

INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF MANAGEMENT OF PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP PROJECTS IN THE SOCIAL FIELD (IN THE CASE OF HIGHER EDUCATION)

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Abstract. *This scientific article discusses issues related to measures to improve the efficiency of the development and management processes of the higher education system, which is considered the most important link in the social sphere, based on public-private partnership projects.*

Keywords: *public-private partnership, higher education system, social sphere, public-private partnership projects.*

Introduction

In recent years, there have been significant positive changes in the mechanisms of public-private partnerships (PPP), particularly in the field of higher education development. When discussing the prospects for the development of PPP in the higher education system, it is essential first to describe the current situation in this system. Currently, there are certain shortcomings in the regulatory and legal frameworks in the education sector, including the lack of market areas for PPP projects proposed in higher education services, as well as the mismatch of financial markets to the needs of PPP (for example, difficulties in obtaining credit resources required to implement PPP projects in higher education, which need long-term investments). Moreover, the absence of public and municipal service staff prepared to implement PPP principles in Uzbekistan hinders the development of the partnership institution.

However, despite this, there are several conditions created for the development of PPP in the higher education system: there is an increasing reestablishment of relations between the state and business within the framework of PPP projects, various expert councils are being formed within state agencies, ministries, and the Senate, and the public sector.

Literature Review. The theoretical and practical aspects of relations between the public and private sectors in PPP have been studied by foreign scholars such as G. Fischer, M. Porter, D. Stiglitz, T. Veblen, J. Keynes, R. Koyz, J. Gelbreit, M. Polanyi, E. Toffler, and Y. Shumpeter. Scientific research by I.A. Irina and E.N. Fanina from the Commonwealth of Independent States has studied modern trends in the development of higher education, addressing the changes in the higher education system during globalization processes, the integration of higher education and practice, the commercialization of higher education results based on scientific research, faculty and student mobility, and the issues of distance education [12]. In Uzbekistan, the development of public services and the formation of vocational and technical education, as well as the development of the PPP mechanism, have been actively researched by economists such as C.C. Gulomov, Q.H. Abdurakhmanov [1], Sh.N. Zaynutdinov [2], N.D. Rahimova, O.Q. Abdurakhmanov, N.K. Zokirova [3], M.Kh. Saidov [4], M.Q. Pardaev [5], B. Turaev [6], N. Yusupov, F.K. Karabaev [7],

U. Djumaniyazov [8], B. Ollanazarov [9], Q. Khalmuratov [10], G. Sadullaeva [11], and others. In addition, N. Yusupov and F.K. Karabaev, within the framework of UNDP projects, have studied the formation of the PPP mechanism, B. Ollanazarov has focused on improving the investment mechanism in tourism sectors, U. Djumaniyazov on improving corporate management in the housing construction sector, and Q. Khalmuratov has conducted research on the organizational and economic mechanism of PPP in the service sector in the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

In the research conducted by scholars of our country, some aspects of the development of the higher education system have been explored. Specifically, in the scientific research carried out by academician S.S. Gulomov, significant attention was paid to establishing effective management of the higher education system and digitizing this system in accordance with international standards [13].

Additionally, B.Yu. Khodiev emphasizes the importance of modern new educational literature in the development of the higher education system. He highlights the need for the gradual development of libraries in higher educational institutions in line with the changing development environment [14]. Taking national characteristics into account, Uzbek economists N. Yusupov and F. Karabaev, within the framework of the UNDP development program, have investigated some theoretical and methodological issues related to the formation and development of PPP. Moreover, U. Djumaniyazov has conducted research aimed at improving corporate governance mechanisms in the housing construction sector under PPP. However, in these studies, the effective implementation and development prospects of PPP mechanisms in the higher education system were not examined as an independent research object. The development of scientifically grounded recommendations and proposals for the introduction of international standards into the higher education system through the application of PPP, which has been effectively implemented in developed foreign countries, remains one of the urgent tasks.

However, in our country, one of the key issues hindering the development of PPP is the unclear role of PPP in modern economic development, especially in the education sector. More specifically, the prospects for the development of PPP in the education sector, the scope and sustainability of PPP projects, the types and institutional and organizational mechanisms for their implementation, and the study of the advantages and disadvantages have not yet been sufficiently explored. Moreover, the mechanisms of interaction between state and higher educational institutions (HEIs) with PPP subjects need further development to fit modern conditions. The efficiency of applying PPP principles in higher education, its future prospects, and trends have not yet been studied as an independent research object. The importance of the chosen topic indicates its relevance.

Research Methodology.

In the process of conducting this scientific research, various methods were used, including scientific observation, abstract-logical thinking, discussions, statistical, economic, financial, and econometric modeling methods.

Analysis and Results.

It is well-known that in recent years, attention to the private sector has been increasing in our country. The transition of some services from the state to the private sector not only improves the quality of services provided in this area but also ensures the efficient use of budgetary resources.

On September 9, 2021, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted Decision No. 563, which outlined measures to increase the coverage of students in higher educational institutions with dormitories. According to this decision, the construction of student dormitories will be carried out based on public-private partnerships, attracting private investment.

Additionally, the decision No. 720, issued on January 30, 2024, by the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, concerning the further improvement and systematization of public-private partnerships, stipulates in Clause 11 of the Regulation on the implementation procedure of PPP projects that any PPP project must be prepared with public discussions in line with the requirements of the relevant government agency, taking into account the interests of the population and consumers of the goods and services provided.

Table 1. Regarding the public discussion of the project for the construction of student dormitories based on public-private partnerships [15].

No.	Name of Higher Education Institution	Coverage of Student Dormitories	Number of Student Dormitories to Be Built	Amount of Funds Allocated	Amount of Subsidy Allocated
1.	Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami	2000	2	150 000,0	50 percent of the value corresponding to one place according to the project-estimate documents, but not exceeding 100 times the base calculation amount
2.	Denov Entrepreneurship and Pedagogical Institute	400	1	32 902,8	50 percent of the value corresponding to one place according to the project-estimate documents, but not exceeding 100 times the base calculation amount
3.	National Institute of Fine Arts and Design named after Kamoliddin Behzod	624	1	49 182,9	50 percent of the value corresponding to one place according to the project-estimate documents, but not exceeding 100 times the base calculation amount

4.	Tashkent Pharmaceutical Institute	720	1	58 949,5	50 percent of the value corresponding to one place according to the project-estimate documents, but not exceeding 100 times the base calculation amount
5.	Namangan State Institute of Foreign Languages	400	1	33 343,1	50% of the value corresponding to one place according to the project-estimate documents, but not exceeding 100 times the base calculation amount.
6.	Navoi State Mining and Technology University	400	1	32 854,9	50% of the value corresponding to one place according to the project-estimate documents, but not exceeding 100 times the base calculation amount.
7.	Termiz State Engineering and Agrotechnology University	400	1	33 046,9	50% of the value corresponding to one place according to the project-estimate documents, but not exceeding 100 times the base calculation amount.
8.	Tashkent State University of Oriental Studies	600	1	46 024,8	50% of the value corresponding to one place according to the project-estimate documents, but not exceeding 100 times the base calculation amount.

9.	Uzbekistan State University of Physical Education and Sports, Fergana Branch	400	1	33 196,7	50% of the value corresponding to one place according to the project-estimate documents, but not exceeding 100 times the base calculation amount.
10.	Uzbekistan State University of Physical Education and Sports, Nukus Branch.	400	1	32 973,1	50% of the value corresponding to one place according to the project-estimate documents, but not exceeding 100 times the base calculation amount.

Based on the above, it has been determined that a total of 502,474.7 soums will be allocated for the construction of student dormitories in 10 state higher educational institutions under public-private partnership (PPP), with a total of 11 student dormitories to be built.

According to the "Uzbekistan - 2030" strategy, the goal is to attract at least 30 billion USD in private investment for PPP projects by 2030. This includes developing the necessary social and economic infrastructure in regions to foster high economic growth and applying successful experiences from PPP projects in electricity production to other sectors. On August 30, 2024, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted Resolution No. PK-308 on "Measures for the Development of Public-Private Partnerships in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2024-2030" [16]. According to Annex 2 of this resolution, a program for projects to be implemented under PPP in 2024-2030 has been approved.

Based on item 8 of this program, with the support of the European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD) and other organizations, the construction of student dormitories for higher education institutions with 17,000 places is planned.

As of today, there are 91 PPP projects in the education sector, totaling 146.70 million USD [17]. To ensure the timely and high-quality implementation of the projects included in the program, and to efficiently manage the funds received by the Public-Private Partnership Fund, a "Public-Private Partnership Projects Center" project office has been established within the structure of the Ministry of Economy and Finance, within the scope of general staffing units. The project office will regularly organize roadshows, roundtable discussions, and other events, make extensive use of international platforms, and arrange training seminars on the requalification and skills development of specialists in PPP, including conducting practical training abroad and organizing the acquisition of international certifications.

Conclusion and Recommendations:

In order to address the existing challenges in the development of PPP in the higher education system, the low economic efficiency of investments required for the construction of social infrastructure objects (dormitories, sports facilities, polyclinics, "Bookcafe," and household

service objects) in higher educational institutions (HEIs) is one of the major barriers to attracting potential private investors.

Therefore, it is crucial to develop mechanisms for granting various benefits, promote the opportunities of PPP projects, and actively disseminate related advertisements and materials in the media.

The analysis conducted for writing this article allowed us to identify the main areas of interaction between the state and private sectors within the framework of PPP projects in higher education:

- Development of educational programs
- Setting requirements for the content of training
- Establishing the job responsibilities and qualification requirements for HEI staff and graduates, as well as professional standards
- Accreditation of programs and independent evaluation of preparation quality
- Targeted training of personnel
- Scientific-production practice and internships for students of HEIs
- Staff training, retraining of teachers, and internships
- Joint research projects
- HEI management
- Financial support in the form of grants and scholarships
- Educational loans
- Targeted capital investment in the financing of HEIs
- Outsourcing non-core functions of HEIs
- Creation/modernization of HEI infrastructure

In conclusion, applying various forms of PPP in the higher education system helps improve the quality and transparency of educational services, facilitates the integration of the latest management technologies into universities, optimizes the allocation of budgetary funds, creates opportunities for modernizing the educational, social, and scientific-innovative infrastructure of HEIs, and accelerates the implementation of information and communication technologies in HEI operations.

REFERENCES

1. Gulyamova S.S., Abdurakhmanova K.Kh. *Education and Human Development: World Practice and Experience of Uzbekistan*. Monograph. – Tashkent: TGEU, 2004. – 170 p.
2. Rakhimova D.N., Abdurakhmanov O.K., Zokirova N.K. *Educational Marketing and the Labor Market*. – Moscow: Sovpismat, 2005. – 144 p.
3. Saidov M.Kh., Peregudov L.V. *Management and Economics of Higher Education*. – Tashkent: Moliya, 2001. – 252 p.
4. M.Q. Pardaev and H.N. Musaev. *Under Editorial Review. Development of Service, Service, and Tourism Sectors: Issues and Solutions*. Monograph. – Tashkent: Iqtisod-Moliya, 2008. – 259 p.
5. Turaev B.Kh. *Organizational-Economic Mechanisms of Regional Tourism*. – Tashkent: Fan, 2009.

6. Sadyullaeva G.S. *Development Prospects of the Education Service Market in Uzbekistan*. "Economics and Innovative Technologies" Scientific-Electronic Journal, No. 6, November-December, 2018.
7. Jumaniyazov U.I. *Improving Corporate Governance Mechanisms in the Field of Housing Construction under Public-Private Partnership*. PhD dissertation, Tashkent State University of Economics, 2017. – 58 p.
8. Ollanazarov B. *Increasing Investment Activity in the Tourism Sector under the Mechanism of Public-Private Partnership*. "Khorezm Mamun Academy Bulletin." – Khiva, 2019. No. 1. pp. 36-41.
9. Khalmuratov Q. *Improving the Organizational-Economic Mechanism of Public-Private Partnership in the Services Sector in the Republic of Karakalpakstan*. PhD dissertation, Nukus: KarSU, 2021. – 63 p.
10. Yusupov N., Karabaev F. *Theory and Practice of Public-Private Partnership*. Educational Module. Ed. by A.E. Shaykhov. – Tashkent, 2013. www.undp.uz
11. Jumaniyazov U.I. *Improving Corporate Governance Mechanisms in the Field of Housing Construction under Public-Private Partnership*. PhD dissertation, Tashkent State University of Economics, 2018. – 27 p.
12. Irina I.A., Fanina E.I. *Modern Trends in the Development of Higher Education*. ISSN: 1991-5497. "World of Science, Culture, and Education" (electronic journal). No. 5 (96), 2022.
13. Ghulomov S.S. *Distance Economic Education*. – Tashkent: Sharq, 2004. – 203 p.
14. Khodiev B.Yu. *Creating Modern Educational Literature for the Higher Economic Education System: New Standard Requirements, Structure, Content*. – Tashkent: TDIU, 2005. – 168 p.
15. www.edu.uz – Official website of the Ministry of Higher Education, Science, and Innovation of Uzbekistan.
16. *Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, dated October 5, 2020, "On Approving the Strategy of Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" and Measures for Its Effective Implementation*. PF-6079. <https://lex.uz/docs/5030957>
17. www.pppda.uz – Official website of the "State-Private Partnership Projects Center" project office.